

Striving for Perfection and Meaning : Family, Idealism, and Spiritual Quest in Tolstoy's Anna Karenina

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Geeta Gupta

Associate Professor
Department Of English
Hindu Kanya
Mahavidyalaya
Jind, Haryana, India

Abstract

"We are not to take Anna Karenina as a work of art; we are to take it as a piece of life. A piece of life it is"¹ (Arnold 176) One of the greatest novels of European literature Anna Karenina encompasses the wide panorama of human life in its varied colours and experiences. Its depth, range, and authenticity of experience make it a semblance of real and vivid life. "The novel is the highest form of human expression so far attained"² (Leavis 11) These words of D. H. Lawrence, as F. R. Leavis quotes it, find their full meaning in the work of Tolstoy's Anna Karenina. The novel, Anna Karenina, embodies the highest form of human thought. It contains the persistent efforts of the writer to seek truth in its various forms. After writing War and Peace, Tolstoy wanted to write a novel based on the period of Peter the Great. But he found himself interested in moral and social concerns of the time. He started writing a novel with a contemporary theme. A novel about a beautiful woman judged and condemned as an unfaithful wife by an unfeeling society. One of the most penetrating explorations of human relationships, moral dilemmas and the tension between individual desire and societal expectations. This paper attempts to examine interwoven themes central to the novel.

Keywords

Love, Spirituality, Fulfilment, Passion, Morality, Family.

Introduction

Anna Karenina portrays the multitude of problems faced by the Russian people. In writing Anna Karenina, Tolstoy endeavoured to bring the whole locale of that era closer to him, It can be called one of the greatest novels of European literature and a representative of the nineteenth-century which "stands at the crucial point where the modern novel begins"³ (Maude XI). Dostoevsky called it an outstanding novel and an unmatched one in the whole of Europe. He called it a perfect artistic production⁴. F. R. Leavis describes the sheer magnitude of Anna Karenina in these words "the greatness and the largeness; the greatness that entails largeness"(Leavis 9). He also says "the relation between art and life it exemplifies for us is the characteristic of the highest kind of creativity."⁵ (Leavis 10)

Tolstoy's search for ultimate veracity in life, doesn't begin in an extraordinary setting but his search takes him to ordinary life, ordinary norms, what Leavis calls 'deep, spontaneous, Lived question'⁶ (Leavis 13) It is the writer's distinctive genius that he has made a novel of contemporary life into an instrument of truth. He doesn't accept conventional answers, rather he scrutinizes life from every point of view. This makes the novel a semblance of life. What Samuel Johnson says about Shakespeare's dramas that they are 'just representations of general nature'⁷ (Johnson 182) is equally true of Anna Karenina. The creative writer's way of arriving at and presenting general truths about life is themes of Anna Karenina that which Tolstoy exemplifies with such resource, such potency, and on such a scale, and there is none to replace or rival it.

Objective of study

The paper attempts to analyse portrayal of complexities of family life, the search for perfection and the spiritual quest for meaning. It aims to examine these themes and how they are interwoven through the novel's characters and narrative structure with special focus on Anna's and Levin's contrasting journey. It seeks to understand how the novelist critiques social ideas and offers a vision of personal growth and spiritual reconciliation amid imperfection.

Review of Literature

Tolstoy's *Anna Karenina* has long been recognised for its profound analysis of family dynamics and personal morality. Scholars have noted two central narratives in the novel relating to Anna's tragic end and gradual spiritual awakening of Levin. The theme of family also occupies major interest in the novel. Critics such as F.R Leavis, Alymer Maude and Tolstoy himself have critiqued and questioned western influences and the concept of progress in the novel.

Tolstoy's pursuit of honest answers makes the novel rise above the ordinary humdrum of life and it scales above the ordinary circumference of moral laws. It is a journey undertaken by novelist where vital questions are asked and an intense search done stopping nowhere else than truth. In a period characterized by crumbling of all norms and values on which the individual stood, a period marked by an intense search for something

substantial to which man could hold on to justify his life, this pursuit of truth is Tolstoy's own longing and striving for ultimate veracity of life in each of his works whether it is artistic or religious, moral or political, and in this endeavour he reaches the upper most peaks of creative perfection in *Anna Karenina*.

Main Text

"Everything was upset in Oblonsky's house"⁸ (1). The following statement in the novel, delineates not only the condition of the Oblonsky's home but that of the contemporary times. It was a time when everything was in shambles from the family life to the economic, social and moral state of the country. In the social milieu, the traditional views regarding up- keeping of children and families were being debased. Marital infidelity had become a practice and a fashion of the times. Characters in the novel like Betsy Tverskaya, fashionable head of her society, not only indulged in the shameful and lewd activities outside marriage but also found it alluring. On the other hand, sensitive to conscience, like Lydia Ivanova who professed to be pure and responsible led a life of hypocrisy, fanaticism and bigotry. Their hearts were dormant and religion was just a shield to cover their dull, mechanical instincts.

In religious sphere, high principles of Christianity and deep, pure urges of the society were giving way to the Pseudo-religion which was represented by the likes of Zhyulya Landau. He was a fake "Clairvoyant" from Paris who muttered something in his half sleep and people took it for the word of God. It is a picture of a society, heading for its moral and spiritual collapse, which decides issues that can be the matter of life and death for an individual on the basis of the senseless talk of a counterfeit. It reveals the horrifying image of chaos in society. In the administrative arena, the bureaucracy with its various ministries, and commissions was likewise inefficient. Projects like irrigation of Zarayskaya province were dragged out for a long time just because it was benefitting some families. Corruption was widespread and it took long to get the work done. In fact the paper work ruled the scene. In such a state, Tolstoy has discussed various themes relevant to the individual and the society. The novel operates at many levels of life; it unites in itself many aspects of life which apparently do not seem to be the subject matter of a love novel. It talks on questions ranging from art, science, Philosophy, and contemporary issues to the intense portrayal of internal passions and emotions. These entire seemingly disjointed things are harmonized by the dexterity of the writer.

The narrative moves through the Russian society and explores its manifold strata from the familial to the social-economic to the spiritual and the moral. On the familial level, Tolstoy discusses problems of love, marriage and marital relationships. On the Socio-Economic level, Tolstoy has delineated various contemporary issues for example, the serf system, conditions of the peasants, the new emerging bourgeois class, decaying aristocracy, inefficient bureaucracy and loopholes in administrative systems. On the moral-spiritual level, Tolstoy has presented various philosophical issues of the time, the existential anguish of the nineteenth-century, the shaking integrity of individual amidst mass of chaos and individual's striving to give meaning to the disorder around him. The artistic achievement of Tolstoy lies in his ability to give a comprehensive and harmonious shape to the novel in spite of the vastness of area he deals with. One level of vision overlaps the other and there is no disjointedness or separateness of issues.

Two separate parallel plots operate in the novels which follow their own path without having any strong line of contact between them. Unity of the novel is upheld by the unity of themes and images in the novel. As against the traditional love novel, it comes out of the milieu of personal relationships into the broad spectrum of human relations in general. The first part of the story concerns with the city life-the urban life of Anna and how she falls in love with Vronsky and leaves her husband and son for him and eventually commits suicide. The other part of the story deals with rural life, the countryside, the story of Levin which is more general and tells us, how he proposed and was initially rejected and finally found fulfilment in the family life.

In spite of its largeness *Anna Karenina* is an organized and planned book. The theme of first twenty-one chapters is the Oblonsky's trouble. It introduces two other issues that of Kitty - Levin - Vronsky and that of Vronsky - Anna theme. The irony of the situation is that Anna who acts as a reconciliatory of her brother and his wife becomes the main factor in breaking the Vronsky - Kitty pair. The bitterness of Shcherbatskis and infidelity of Oblonsky germinate the seed of Anna's tragedy and prepares the audience for the final catastrophe. Later Oblonsky's affair is patched up and Kitty marries Levin. The pair of Kitty and Levin proves to be successful and an ideal pair whereas Anna deserts her husband and elopes with Vronsky. Finally, it leads to Anna's tragedy and Levin's fulfilment. Chapter by chapter, through series of events, Tolstoy scrutinizes life. Seven relationships between seven characters are delineated in the novel. These seven relationships pair and Impair at different times. Being an odd number one is always left out. In the beginning Kitty and Levin are left out and Karenin pair is threatened by Vronsky and later Kitty and Levin get married, Vronsky and Anna unite and Karenin is left out.

Tolstoy has discussed issues of marriage and family and delineates three marriages and explores the man woman relationship through them. The marriage of Dolly and Oblonsky, a conventional marriage, operates according to the various accepted norms of the society. It introduces the theme of marital infidelity. The second marriage of Anna and

Karenin is a failure and ushers in the seeds of tragedy. Whereas the marriage of Kitty and Levin results in fulfilment and a consummate relationship between them. In Oblonsky's case, marriage is just an establishment of the commonplace norms of the society. It is just a patch up, a conventional compromise to obtain a working relationship. As against this stagnant, common and customary establishment of the social norms, we are introduced to Anna and Levin, who rise above the habitual lethargy of the common place into the realm of intense passion, love and idealism. Anna unlike Dolly can't accept the falsity of her position and her stagnant life with Karenin whereas Levin wants a stable life with Kitty unlike Oblonsky and a marriage with love unlike the Karenins. The delicate relationships between husband and wife are portrayed subtly and with sensitivity. The sacred relationship of marriage can only be sustained when it is based on foundation of truth and love; otherwise it debases itself into the realms of falsehood and deceit. Marriage without love and love without marriage both are detrimental to the growth of true man woman relationships. The marriage of Dolly and Steve, Anna and Karenin, and Love of Anna and Vronsky without true basis of marriage is evocative of pathos and it exposes its falsehood whereas Love and subsequent marriage of Kitty and Levin fulfils the conjugal relationship and gives marital bliss.

The other theme related to marriage that is of family, is dealt with in the novel; The novel is chiefly a family work. Its drama begins in a family, does not go beyond it and it ends there too. Whether in the positive sense (the English novel) or the negative sense (the French novel), it is the family which always plays the leading role in a novel. Tolstoy considered family as a sacred institution which protects the individual's integrity and is a basic unit of community living. In the crumbling and decaying times, his hopes were centered on the family which could provide a venue for the spiritual and moral growth of the individual. Tolstoy believed in the sacred ties that bind people in a family and the selfless love, care and protection that it provides. The theme of 'family' is the major theme in the novel. His earlier works also depict in various measures his respect and concern for the family life. Apart from the social and moral association with the family, it was deeply related to his religious Christian belief. He had a broad moral - spiritual vision of the 'family' and 'home' which connotated for him feelings of life, happiness and purity. He never saw family with narrow or sentimental outlook but saw it as an ideal.

"All happy families resemble one another, but each unhappy family is unhappy in its own way"⁹(1) The major motif of family is introduced in the first line of the novel; it is the thematic interest in the family life that binds the novel as a whole. The two parallel stories of Anna and Vronsky, and Kitty and Levin though each running a separate course is united thematically as both of them are concerned with family. The progress of both the stories is parallel whereas the family life of Anna and Vronsky ends in catastrophe, the marriage life of Kitty and Levin finds fulfilment in the family. In the beginning both Anna and Vronsky, and Kitty and Levin, are separated and in the latter half of the novel both unite. The various stages of the union of both the couples are characterized by the same phases of separation and union. Tolstoy considered marriage and family life as more significant ground to test the integrity and love of an individual as against pure individual romance. The union of two individuals, their sharing of responsibilities and bringing up of children was an ideal way of sharing love and giving meaning to life. In Anna Karenina we find Kitty and Levin, Anna and Vronsky being tested in the crucible of married life and facing various dilemmas together. In fact, family becomes the centre where moral integrity of an individual is tested; spiritual upheavals ensue, representing both bondage and freedom.

People like Steve Oblonsky, Dolly, Betsy and Karenin flow with the stream of life, leading mechanical lives without questioning life and its paradoxes. It is an animal existence. Sometimes they may rise above the maze of routine and manners but these moments are few and rare. In the living bubbling stream of life with its all engulfing routine of birth, marriage, procreation and death, only a few people stop to ponder over questions as "why live? They transcend the motley mentality to reach for the meaning of life. They give pattern and order to their life and make sense out of the nonsense. Life may or may not reveal itself to them but certainly their life becomes a great adventure in itself. Such people are few but they leave their mark on life.

The theme for spiritual fulfilment is embodied in the characters of Anna and Levin who experience the intensity of the moment and give their life to it. They are endowed with writer's vision of life. Both the characters endorse their own ways to give shape to their inner urges. Whereas the quest for spiritual perfection is explicit in Levin, it is implicit in Anna. Levin represents the skeptic man in Tolstoy himself. He is a true representative of the nineteenth century dilemma time when the old values were disintegrating and the new not able to sustain man. Darwin's Origin of Species had caused havoc in the conventional attitudes. Religion which earlier played Levin finds that old traditions and religion which earlier used to answer Man's basic queries were now ruined under the impact of new scientific theories. But the new scientific theories themselves were unable to explain the vital questions as, why is man born? And, what he is born for?

Levin's quest for spiritual perfection is a deep urge within him to cling to something substantial. A genuine person he belongs to good, old aristocratic family. The main trait that differentiates Levin from other characters is his simplicity. He is the man who's inner self shines through the outer. His manners are not a veil to cover his real - self. His continuous introspecting nature makes him suspect his motives relentlessly. He leads a

natural life measured by the rhythms of seasons. His world is a natural world as against artificial world of cities. He is rooted in tradition as against the rootlessness of Anna, Vronsky and Steve Oblonsky who have no proper family background. Levin also represents the general discontent and frustration prevalent in the nineteenth century. The important issues concerning various socio political themes are connected with Levin. Levin finds that traditional religious faith that nourishes most of the people including his wife is deeply embedded in him. Birth and Death provoke him as the eternal mysteries to be resolved. He is continuously bewildered by the business of the world, what is it all for? All his life becomes a pursuit, a search for spiritual perfection.

Quest for spiritual perfection is an intense desire which touches the inmost core of one's being. It is a soulful yearning for a fulfilment beyond the senses, mind and intellect. It is a passionate communion with what is really True, Beautiful and Eternal. To Anna, it was love that could confer on her this rich experience beyond all barriers of space and Time. Anna journeys through the path of love to reach the realms of perfection. But Anna's attempt becomes an abortive one. An attempt thwarted by the mediocrity and average attitude of the surroundings. It is Anna's supreme effort to find salvation in love. To give her up to the one word 'love' and be oblivious to everything else. But, corrupt society which weighs appearances more than reality crushes her totally and she becomes its hapless victim. A nineteenth century society with false views and values, with its ambivalent attitude and hypocrisy condemns open true human relationships while it closes its eyes and even approves clandestine affairs. Anna is not a woman who can give herself half way but the 'word' for her is 'completeness' and 'fulfilment'. Unable to accept the social conventions that direct her to deceit and guilt she prefers to live a life where she doesn't have to take support of falsehood.

Anna's marriage was just an arrangement of convenience; a routine which with passage of time had become a habit. She had never realized her potency of love and her intense passionate nature. It was veiled under the cover of conventional marriage where love had no part to play. She got satisfaction as mother of Sergei whom she loved and cared for but the woman in her who had till then never tasted the true conjugal bliss, realized her true need, when she meets Vronsky. Though initially the nature of their attraction can be as most often it is in such relationships, a mutual attraction but later for Anna it became a quest in itself. A quest for fulfilment through love. She sacrificed her family life, son, respect, and society, everything for love. A love that for her has transcended the physical barriers and connoted something higher and spiritual, where she can find final consummation. But alas, the object of her love was not worth her. Vronsky, an average man couldn't transcend his conventional ideas. If Anna would have been an ordinary woman, maybe she would have been satisfied by Vronsky, but Anna as she was an intelligent, beautiful, and passionate and essentially a moral lady couldn't cope with the odds that she encountered.

A lady who could have ruled the hearts of people, leaves everything to experience love that she had been denied. But nineteenth century pseudo morality would never accept a woman who has left her husband. Vronsky like Anna couldn't live on love alone. For an average man like him a social context and social recognition was necessary. Hypocritical society accepts Vronsky easily but it condemns Anna. Anna, who finds that a social context is necessary for her because Vronsky needs society, finds herself dangling between two spheres, none providing fulfilment. She had lost for all practical purposes her first born child, respect and finally she feels that she is on the verge of losing the one for whom she had left all. Her quest for 'Love' that had been an ideal for her, a cherished object, in the final moment brings disillusionment.

She is faced with dreariness and how in the eyes of all she was a degraded woman. The men, who had deliberately had affairs, were not only condoned but it was considered natural and inoffensive. The world had one socio moral standard for man and another for woman. Love to man is not paramount, it may at best be his need but to woman, love is all. If Anna is condemned then needless to say, all the men characters also be condemned for their deliberate though casual moral lapses. Tolstoy's sympathy for Anna is evident, but it was nineteenth - century Russia which laid its constraints on the writer. It is this honest approach to the contemporary problems, totally candid, and realistic, that makes the novel a vivid, vital; sensitive, and intense drama of life. Anna becomes the pitiable and pathetic sacrificial offering at the altar of love. If the novel is an unforgettable experience, then Anna is an integral part of it.

Conclusion

Tolstoy presents a complete picture of life. A picture embodying struggles and failures, grief and happiness. A replete teeming life mirroring life itself. The characters of the novel are real characters of flesh and bone; heart and soul, who have their own grief, sorrows, joys and happiness. They are true to life, not giant or dwarfs and are the products of the writer's acute sensibility. They live in a social context and it is the environment they inhabit and the relations they form that determine their actions and responses. They move the reader because they are immensely near to the reader and the reader knows them as he knows his own friend or relation. It is a vast world that Tolstoy creates and we find an array of major and minor characters creating life itself.

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